

Assessment of the Usage of Social Media by Secondary School Students in Selected Schools in Nasarawa State

Lega Agbadu Hassan

Department of Mass Communication, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

Email: hassleg2016@gmail.com

08035046641

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20076946>

Abstract

The study “Assessment of the Usage of Social Media by Secondary School Students in selected schools in Nasarawa State,” sets out to examine the use of social media among secondary school students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, with particular attention to the platforms most frequently accessed and the implications of such usage on their social interaction and academic activities. A survey design was adopted for the study, while data were collected through the use of structured questionnaire administered to students in the selected schools. The findings revealed that a significant number of secondary schools students actively engaged with various social media platforms. Among the platforms most commonly used are Facebook, Whatsapp, TikTok, Instagram, and X(formerly Twitter). The study indicates that many students spend at least thirty minutes or more daily interacting on these platforms. The study also showed that students activities on social media vary widely and included posting or commenting on friends' profiles, exchanging messages, chatting with peers, playing online games, sharing documents and multimedia files, watching short videos, and occasionally communicating with teachers regarding academic matters. These interactions demonstrate that social media has become an integral part of students' daily routines and social engagement. The results further suggest that social media usage among secondary school students has both constructive and adverse effects. On positive side, the platforms provide opportunities for maintaining friendships, strengthening social networks, and facilitating communication among peers and teachers. They also offer access to educational materials and information that may support learning. However, the study also identified several concerns, such as excessive engagement with social media may divert students' attention from academic tasks, reduce study time, and expose them to inappropriate content that could influence behaviour and values negatively. Consequently uncontrolled use may contribute to declining academic focus and encourage undesirable social tendencies. Based on these findings, the study concludes that social media plays a significant role in shaping the social and academic experiences of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. While the technology offers useful opportunities for the communication and learning, it also presents challenges that require proper monitoring and guidance. The study therefore recommends that government agencies strengthen policies on internet regulation and digital safety. In addition, school administrators should organise regular workshops, seminars, and awareness programmes for students and parents to educate them on responsible social media usage and its implications for academic performance and personal development.

Keywords: Social Media, Secondary School Students, Nasarawa State, Usage

Introduction

Advancements in technology have brought about swift and far-reaching changes across the globe, making digital tools as primary avenue for accessing and sharing knowledge. The growth of internet technology coupled with its increasing affordability, has contributed significantly to the widespread adoption of social media as dominant channels of communication. Owing to their interactive features, these platforms enable users to exchange ideas and information seamlessly. According to Jones (2000), social media consist of online communities where internet users interact with others who share similar interests, whether from personal, professional or academic. This suggests that social media facilitate connections among individuals who may be geographically distant yet united by common goals or concerns.

Social networking sites have practically actualised the concept of the "global village," allowing millions of people to communicate across borders. However, alongside these technological advancements are emerging challenges, particularly the erosion of certain core values, especially among students who constitute a large proportion of active users. Adam, Zor, and Oye (2012) explain that online social networking platforms are designed to establish and maintain relationships among individuals with shared interests and activities.

In educational settings today, Whatsapp has become a widely used platform. Lecturers and Teachers often utilise group chats to disseminate relevant academic information, while students, especially classmates or members of the same cohort, use these groups to exchange updates and materials among themselves. Although social networking platforms are increasingly recognised as valuable educational resources, research indicates that many students primarily engage with sites such as Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram for leisure activities, including entertainment, passing time, maintaining existing friendships, or forming new ones (Ellison, Steinfield & Lampe, 2007). While some students attribute declining academic performance to the significant amount of time spent on social networking sites (Kimberly, 2009), only a limited number may fully appreciate the academic and professional opportunities these platforms provide.

Schill (2011) observes that social media platforms like Facebook can foster undersirable habits among teenagers, such as procrastination - spending excessive time interacting with friends online, and potentially other negative behaviours. It has become increasingly common to observe students dedicating long hours to social media activities on Facebook, TikTok, WhatsApp and X(formerly Twitter), and similar platforms at the expense of their academic responsibilities. As these platforms continue to expand in popularity, technology remains an essential component of contemporary student life and success. Consequently, scholars have devoted substantial research attention to examining the influence of social media on students' academic performance and retention in tertiary institutions. Parents today often express concern that their children devote excessive time to Facebook, TikTok, and other social networking platforms rather than concentrating adequately on their studies.

In Nigeria , millions of users engage daily with platforms such as Facebook, Whatsapp, TikTok, Instagram, and X(formerly Twitter), generating significant positive and negative effects on individuals and society at large.

Statement of the Problem

The degree of privacy and freedom available on social media platforms present a significant concern for scholars and educators. Some researchers observe that students who maintain Facebook and Instagram connections often demonstrate patterns that may influence their academic and social engagement. For instance,

Ajewole and Fasola (2012), drawing on Hodo (2011), argue that there is a growing trend of excessive social networking among people. The rising degree of participation in social media, especially among college students who spend considerable time building and maintaining online friendships and social connections - seems to carry significant consequences for their daily lives. Evidence from their findings suggests that students who frequently use platforms such as Facebook and other social networking sites tend to allocate less time to their studies and may consequently record lower academic performance compared to those who do not actively engage with these platforms. Such patterns, if not carefully monitored, could negatively affect students' academic progress, social relationships, and even their spiritual development.

In the same vein, Kalpidou, Costin and Morris (2011) reinforce this perspective by emphasising that extensive participation in social networking can influence students' academic outcomes and overall social life. Against this backdrop, the present study seeks to examine the extent to which secondary school students utilise social media, focusing particularly on the amount of time they spend online, the nature of their activities, and the resulting impact on their moral and academic development within today's digital era.

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the study seeks to:

5. Identify the types of social media platforms secondary school students visit the most and how often they visit such sites.
6. Ascertain the factors that attract secondary school students to social media.
7. Establish the extent to which social media interfere with secondary school students' academic life.
8. Assess the impact of social media on the social life of the students.

Research Questions

Based on the objectives of the study, the research questions below guided the study:

1. What social media platforms do secondary school students in Nasarawa State visit the most and how often do they visit such sites?
 2. What are the factors that attract secondary school students in Nasarawa State to social media?
 3. Do social media interfere with the academic performance of secondary school
4. What implication do social media have on the social life of students?

Scope of the Study

The researcher divided all the secondary schools in Nasarawa State into three (3) groups (strata) based on the three senatorial zones of the state.

- Nasarawa North
- Nasarawa South
- Nasarawa West

After grouping the schools according to these zones, the researcher then select three schools from each senatorial zone. This ensure that all the zones of the state are fairly represented in the study, with emphasis on secondary school students who have access to social media platforms. Therefore, the method used is Stratified Random Sampling Techniques.

The 9 selected schools are:

- I. Government Science School, Lafia.
- II. Government College, Lafia
- III. Government Secondary School Maina, Lafia
- IV. Government Secondary School, Akwanga
- V. Government Secondary School, Akwanga North
- VI. Government Secondary School, Akwanga South
- VII. Government Secondary School, Mararaba Gurku
- VIII. Government Secondary School, Masaka
- IX. Government Secondary School, Nyanya Gbagyi

Review of Literature

Review of Concepts

The following concepts are reviewed: New Media and Social Media.

New Media

The concept new media emerged toward the end of the late twentieth century and is used to describe technological innovations that span various sectors of the media industry. Flew (2002), explains that technologies classified as new media are largely digital in nature and possess qualities such as interactivity, networking capability, compressibility, density, and the ability to be modified or manipulated. Typical examples include the Internet, websites, digital multimedia, video games, CD-ROMs, and DVDs.

Scholars approach the concept of new media from diverse perspectives Manovich (2001) provides a comprehensive overview by identifying eight key dimensions of them. Among these are the distinction between new media and cyberculture, new media as computer-based distribution platforms, and new media as digitally encoded content governed by software. He further argues that culture products that depend on digital representation and computer-based dissemination share certain fundamental characteristics.

Croteau and Hoynes (2003) suggest that the rise of digital technologies represents a potentially transformative shift in the control of information, experiences, and resources. In their view, these developments broaden public access to information,

enabling individuals to obtain content quickly and conveniently regardless of geographical location. They also note that new media weaken the traditional link between physical space and social interaction, thereby reducing the importance of geographical boundaries in shaping relationships. In globalised environment, new media provide individuals with numerous options through which they can shape their lifestyle and values.

Social Media

Social media refer to Internet-based platforms that allow users to create personal or semi-public profile within a defined online environment, connect with other users, and interact through shared links and networks. Users can view their own connections as well as those established by others, although the form and description of these connections may differ across platforms (Boyd and Ellison, 2007)..

According to Mbaeze, Elochukwu, & Chioma (2010), social media can also be described as social structures consisting of individuals or organisations known as "nodes," which are linked through various forms of relationships. These relationships may include friendships, family ties, shared interests, financial transactions, beliefs knowledge exchange, prestige, or even personal sentiments.

Asemah, Okpanachi & Edegoh (2013), as cited in Adeboye (2012) note that social networking platforms provide opportunities for users to share personal experiences and creative content such as music, videos, and other multi media materials with a wider audience. Presently, some of the most widely used platforms include Facebook, Whatsapp, TikTok, X(formerly Twitter), and Instagram. Although these platforms have become more advanced over time, online social interaction itself is not a recent development; people began engaging and communicating with one another via the internet shortly after emergence.

Review of Empirical Works

This section review previous empirical work of other scholars related to the current study.

To investigate how students engage with social networking sites (SNSs) and the consequences of such use, Tham and Ahmed (2011) conducted a study titled *The Usage and Implications of Social Networking Sites: Survey of college students*. The research examined patterns of SNS use, students perceptions of online communications, and their awareness of the effects of SNS engagement on academic achievement and personal growth. Using a non-properbility sample of 445 students drown from St. Cloud State University, Minnesota, data were collected during the spring semester of 2011. The findings indicated that female students devoted more time to social networking platforms than their male counterparts. Generally, time spent on SNSs declined as respondents' age increase. Age differences were also observed in students' perceptions of how SNS use influenced their academic performance, with younger students more likely to report negative academic effects. The study further identified significant relationships between age, gender and perceptions of the impact of SNSs on personal development. Class standing and field of study were also associated with variations in perceived influence. Moreover, higher rate of SNS use were positively related to networking with friends, family, and professional contacts, whereas negative relationships were identified between SNS usage and activities such

as seeking volunteer opportunities and awareness of others' efforts to find romantic partners online. Age was positively associated with networking activities and awareness of cyberbullying experiences, but negatively associated with awareness of others' use of SNSs for dating purposes. Overall, students' perceptions of SNS influence largely corresponded with the empirical patterns identified in the study.

In a related investigation, Ogundiji (2014) examined *Use of Social Networking among Secondary School Students: Implications for Academic Performance* in Lagos State, Nigeria. The research focused on public and private secondary school students and explored the connection between social networking engagement and factors affecting their academic outcomes. A survey research design was adopted to facilitate the connection of data through questionnaire and academic records. The study population comprised secondary school students across Lagos State, from which sample of 240 students was selected from 12 schools located in three Local Government Areas, representing approximately 15% of LGAs. Twenty students were randomly selected from each school. Both primary and secondary data were utilised: questionnaire structured on five-point Likert Scale served as the primary data source, while students' Mathematics and English achievement across constituted the secondary data. Academic performance was categorised into grade bands ranging from A (excellent) to F (poor), and subsequently grouped into high (A - B), average (C - D), and below-average categories. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, factor analysis, cross-tabulation, and regression techniques. The results revealed that time spent on SNSs did not have a statistically significant effect on students' academic performance. Similarly, classroom participation did not significantly predict average achievement in Mathematics and English. However, the number of online friends significantly influenced the time devoted to SNSs, while frequency of posting was not meaningful predictor of classroom participation. Demographic variables were not found to significantly affect academic performance among SNS users, although overall SNS use demonstrated a significant relationship with academic outcomes. Based on these findings, the study recommended increased sensitisation initiative, such as seminar and symposium, to educate students and parents about the potential adverse effects of excessive SNS use on academic performance. It further advised school authorities to regulate SNS access and use during school hours and encouraged the Ministry of Education to establish and enforce clear guidelines governing social media use within secondary schools. Despite the valuable contributions of these studies, the literature suggests that inadequate attention has been paid to the broader consequences of unrestricted social media usage among secondary school students and the issue of responsibility for monitoring such usage. While previous researchers have made commendable efforts, the lingering concerns regarding the unregulated use of social media by younger users highlight a significant gap. Addressing this gap provides the essential justification for undertaking a study of this nature, with the aim of extending existing knowledge and offering practical solutions to the identified shortcomings.

Theoretical Framework

According to McQuail (2000), a theory can be described as an organised collection of related ideas, concepts, explanations, and proportions developed to clarify and forecast particular phenomenon. The relevance of theory in a study of this kind cannot be overstated, as it provides the foundation upon which the research is structured and interpreted. Therefore this study is grounded on Uses and Gratifications Theory.

Uses and Gratifications (UGT). Uses and Gratifications Theory is widely acknowledged as a strand within media effects scholarship, as noted by McQuail (1994). In the formative years of communication research, scholars began to examine the specific rewards that draw audiences to particular media channels and content types that address their social and psychological expectations. Rather than concentrating solely on what media do to people, this perspectives investigates what people do with media, especially how they utilise media to fulfil intellectual, emotional, personal, and entertainment-related needs. Rubin (2002) further explains that uses and gratifications approach views audiences as purposeful and active participants. Individuals deliberately select media platforms and messages in line with their specific motives and objectives. This perspectives underscores that media consumption is guided by by personal and social motivation, which in turn influence patterns of selection, attention, and engagement. Consequently, the theory shifts the focus of influence from the media to the audience, rejecting the assumption that media exert uniform and automatic effects on all users. Within the context of this study, the theory provides a useful framework for understanding the reasons students engage with social media. It helps to reveal the motivations that drive their use of these platforms for sharing ideas, interacting, and exchanging various forms of content. Additionally, it explains how students rely on social networking platforms to satisfy communication needs and maintain relationships, thereby uncovering the fundamental purposes behind their online interactions with peers.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted the survey approach, a branch of descriptive research design. The target population comprised secondary school students selected from nine schools across the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State. According to records obtained from the Nasarwa State Ministry of Education, Latia (2020), the total student population of the selected schools stood at 10,013. Consequently, this figure of 10,013 students constituted the population for the study.

Method of data collection

The study adopted the questionnaire as the method of data collection, where structured questions were administered to secondary school students in the selected schools to obtain relevant data for the study. The study utilised a structured questionnaire as the primary research instrument for data collection. In addition, the research drew on secondary sources of data, including relevant previous studies, textbooks, scholarly journal articles, and materials obtained from the Internet, to support and enrich the analysis.

Sample Size

The sample size for the study was computed using the Fisher formula estimating proportions, as reported by Habib, Magruder-Habib, and Kupper (1987). The formula is presented as follows:

$$n = z^2 pq / d^2$$

Where

n = desired size where the population under study is more than 10,000

z = standard normal deviation

P = proportion of target population estimated to practical characteristics from a previous similar study. Where none exists, $p = 50\%$ or 0.5

$q = (1 - p)$

d = Degree of accuracy = 5% or 0.05

Therefore, the sample size is

$$(1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times (1 - 0.5) / (0.05)^2$$

$$(1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5 / 0.0025$$

$$n = 3.8416 \text{ or } 384 \text{ approximately}$$

Consequently, 384 respondents were sampled for this study

Tables 1: Selected secondary schools in Southern Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State

SOUTHERN SENETORIAL ZONE		
	Name of School	No. of Students
1	Government Science School, Lafia	1,203
2	Government Collage, Lafia	1,250
3	Government Secondary School Maina, Lafia	3,160
Total		6,613

Table 2: Selected secondary schools in Northern Senatorial Zone, Nasarawa State

NORTHERN SENETORIAL ZONE		
	Name of School	No. of Students
1	Government Secondary School, Akwanga	418
2	Government Secondary School, Akwanga North	441
3	Government Secondary School, Akwanga South	903
Total		1,962

Table 3: Selected secondary schools in Western Sanatorial Zone, Nasarawa State

WESTERN SENETORIAL ZONE		
	Name of School	No. Of Students
1	Government Secondary School Mararaba Gurku	596
2	Government Secondary School Masaka	1088
3	Government Secondary School NyanyaGbagi	754
Total		2,438

Source: Field work, 2020 total no. of students in the nine selected schools = **10,013**

Presentation of Data Analysis

A total of 384 copies of questionnaire administered to respondents for the purpose of the study. Out of this number, 357 questionnaire distributed personally by the researcher with the assistance of trained research assistants were properly completed and considered suitable for the analysis, representing, a response rate of 92.97%. However, 27 copies representing 7.03%, were either not returned or were incorrectly filled and consequently regarded as invalid. Accordingly, the 357 valid questionnaire constituted the data for the analysis.

Table 4: Demography of Respondents

S/N	Demography	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender		
	Male	194	54.34
	Female	163	45.66
	Total	357	100
2	Age		
	Below 15	152	42.58
	16 to 19	132	36.97
	20 above`	73	20.45
	Total	357	100

Source: Field work, 2020

Table 4 present the demographic data of respondents of students 194 (54.34%) respondents are males while 163 (45.66%) respondents are females and the age distribution of respondents with 152 (42.58%) are below the age of 15 years. 132 (36.97%) respondents fall between the age of 16 to 19 years while 73(20.45%) respondents are above 20 years

Table 5: Social media platforms respondents visit the most

Responses	Frequency	Percentage %
Facebook	140	39.22
WhatsApp	69	19.32
Instagram	41	11.49
TikTok	34	9.52
X (formerly Twitter)	62	17.37
Others	11	3.08
Total	357	100

Source: Field work, 2020

As seen from table 5 above, which sought to know the social media platform visited the most by respondents. Results indicate that 140 (39.22%) respondents visit Facebook, more frequently than other social media platforms, 69(19.32%) averred that they visit WhatsApp more frequently, 41(11.49%) respondents visit Instagram more frequently, 34(9.52%) use TikTok the most, 62(17.37%) respondents use X (formerly Twitter) the most, while 11(3.08%) respondents use others.

Table 6: What respondents do on social media platform

Responses	Frequency	Percentage %
Making comments on friends	61	17.09
Receiving and sending messages	96	26.89
Chatting with friends	76	21.29
Playing games	44	12.32
Sharing files	21	5.88
Watching Pornography	3	0.84
Communication with teachers	17	4.76
Communication with friends about academic interest	39	10.93
Total	357	100

Source: Field work, 2020

Table 6 sought from respondents the activities that dominate their interaction on social media. Results shows that 61 (17.09%) of the respondents averred that making comments on friends profile was the activity that dominate their interaction on social media platforms, 96 (26.89%) averred that receiving and sending messages dominated their activities on social media, 76 (21.29%) averred that chatting with friends dominated their activities, 44 (12.32%) averred that playing games was their predominant activity on social media platforms, 21 (5.88%) respondents averred that sharing files was top on the activities that dominate their activities on social media.

Other results show that 3 (0.84%) respondents are of the view that watching pornography dominated their activities on social media platforms, 17 (4.76%) assert that interacting with teachers dominated their activities while 39 (10.92%) are of the view that communication about academic interest dominated their activities on social media platforms. This implies that a lot of activities dominate the interaction of secondary school students in Nasarawa State.

Table 7: Amount of time spent on social media platforms by respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage %
Less than an hour	87	24.37
1 to 2 houses	114	31.93
3 to 4 hours	97	27.17
More than 5 hours	59	16.52
Total	357	100

Source: Field work, 2020

In a bid to identify the extent of time devoted to social media platforms by respondents, responses show that 87 (24.37%) respondents spend less than an hour on social media platforms, 114 (31.93%) spend between 1 to 2 hours, 97 (27.17%) respondents spend between 3 to 4 hours while 59 (16.52%) spend more than 5 hours on social media platforms.

Table 8: Impact of social media on respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage %
Positive	283	79.27
Negative	52	14.57
Neutral	22	6.16
Total	357	100

Source: Field work, 2020

Table 8 sought from respondents the impact of social media on them. Results show that 283 (79.27%) respondents averred that the impact of social media on them was positive, 52 (14.57%) said the impact was negative while 22 (6.16%) said the impact was indifferent.

Table 9: How social media have affected respondents' academic performance

Responses	Frequency	Percentage %
Positive	78	21.85
Negative	187	52.38
Neutral	92	25.77
Total	357	100

Source: Field work, 2020

Table 9 indicate that 78 (21.85%) respondents averred that social media platforms have positively affected their academic performance, 187 (52.38%) think otherwise; they are of the view that social networking sites have negatively affected their academic performance while 92 (25.77%) respondents are neutral on the effect of social media platforms on their academic performance.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the pattern of social media usage among secondary school students in Nasarawa State, with particular focus on the amount of time spent online, the nature of activities engage in, and the perceived effects on their social and academic

lives. Specifically, the research identified the social media platforms most frequently accessed by students and the regularity of their visits; investigated the factors that attract students to these platforms; explored the gratifications derived from their usage; and determined the extent to which social media engagement influences academic performance. Following a careful administration and analysis of the research instruments, the following findings emerged:

i. The study revealed that students between the ages of 15 and 19 constituted the group that spent the greatest amount of time on social media. The platforms most commonly visited were Facebook, Whatsapp, TikTok, and Instagram, with many students spending a considerable portion of their daily time on these sites. This findings aligns with Ogundiji (2014), whose study on the use of social networking sites among Secondary School Students reported that the duration of time spent online did not significantly determine academic performance. Nevertheless, the present study showed that most respondents spent at least thirty minutes per day socialising through online chats. It was further observed that younger students frequently used social media as a means of maintaining friendships with former classmates and friends from their local communities.

ii. The findings indicated that predominant activities carried out by students on social media included commenting on friends' profile, sending and receiving messages, chatting, playing games, sharing files, viewing pornographic content, interacting with teachers, and discussing academic matters. Among these, messages and chatting were the most prevalent activities. These results are consistent with the work of Ellison, Steinfield and Lampe (2007), who observed that students primarily use social networking platforms such as Facebook for entertainment, passing time, sustaining existing friends, and forming new ones. Similarly, Acquisti and Gross (2006), noted that young people are motivated to join social networking sites to maintain close friendships, reinforce new social ties, and, to lesser extent, establish new relationships online.

iii. Perceived Positive Impact. The study revealed that a substantial proportion of respondents (283, representing 79.27%) reported that social media had a positive influence on their lives. This suggests that many students perceive benefits such as enhanced communication, access to information, and social connectivity as outcomes of their engagement with social networking platforms.

iv. Finally, despite the perceived positive benefits, the study also found that social media usage had a negative effect on students' academic performance. A total of 187 respondents (52.38%), indicated that their academic performance declined since they began actively engaging with social media platforms. The data suggest that excessive use of social media can serve as distraction, thereby reducing the time and attention devoted to academic activities. Furthermore, many students acknowledged that their academic outcomes have not been as satisfactory since they became frequent users of social media. This findings corroborates the position of Ajewole and Fasola (2012), expressed concern over the increasing obsession with social media networking among young people and its potential adverse consequences on their academic, social-cultural, and spiritual development if left unchecked.

To sum up, while social media provide social and informational benefits to secondary school students in Nasarawa State, their excessive or uncontrolled usage poses significant risks to academic performance.

Summary

This research examined the degree to which secondary school students in Nasarawa State engage with social media, focusing particularly on the amount of time they devote to these platforms, the nature of their activities online, and the implications for their social interaction and academic performance. The study aimed to determine the social media platforms most frequently accessed by students and the regularity of such usage.

A survey research design adopted, employing a multi-stage sampling approach that combined quota and simple random sampling techniques. Using Fisher's formula for sample size determination, a total of 357 respondents were selected. Questionnaire were administered to the respondent to obtain relevant data for the study. The research was grounded in the Uses and Gratifications Theory. Data obtained were analysed using frequency tables and percentage distribution. The findings revealed that secondary school students in Nasarawa States commonly use platforms platforms such as Facebook, Whatsapp, Instagram, TikTok, X(formerly Twitter), among others. Many of the students spend a significant portion of their day on these platforms. Their online activities largely involve commenting on friends' profile, sending and receiving messages, chatting, playing games, sharing files, viewing explicit content, interacting with teachers, and discussing academic matters. Among these activities, sending and receiving messages ranked highest, followed by chatting with friends and commenting on profiles.

The study further identified several factors that motivate students' engagement with social media. These include maintaining friendships, occupying leisure time, discussing academic issues, and general socialisation. In terms of gratifications, students reported satisfaction from messaging, chatting with peers, and participating in intellectually stimulating discussions.

However, the results indicate that social media usage has had a predominantly negative impact on students' academic achievement. It was observed that social media often functions as a source of distraction, thereby contributing to declining academic performance. Notably, 52.38% of the respondents acknowledged that their academic results had deteriorated since they began actively using social media platforms.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes that social media plays a significant role in shaping the social and academic experiences of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. While the technology offers useful opportunities for communication and learning, it also presents challenges that require proper monitoring and guidance. This is evident in students' growing tendency to spending more time online interacting, such as maintaining friendships and staying connected with peers, rather than engaging with educational resources and academic content. When not properly guided or monitored, social media can become a major source of distraction and may contribute to moral decline through exposure to inappropriate or misleading materials shared online.

The findings therefore highlight the need for greater awareness and deeper understanding of how social media affects students' academic achievements and moral development. School administrators must pay close attention not only to the platforms students use but also to the broader influence these platforms exert on their behaviour and learning outcomes. Although social media can divert students' attention from schoolwork and other academic obligations, it also offers valuable educational opportunities when used responsibly.

In summary, social media can be viewed as a double-edged sword, possessing both beneficial and harmful potentials for students. Consequently, the involvement of parents, teachers, and religious leaders remains crucial in guiding young people and reducing the negative impacts associated with improper social media use.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

4. **Seminar and Awareness Programmes:** School Management should organise seminars, workshops and public lectures to educate students and parents about the implications of social media use within and outside the school environment . Such programmes will promote responsible and informed usage.
5. **Controlled internet Access:** School authorities should introduce structured guidelines for social media usage, such as limiting access to specific period like break times or providing regulated internet access where facilities exist. Rather than imposing a total ban, clear policies and time restrictions should be established to encourage discipline and responsible engagement.
6. **Regulation Framework:** The government, through the Ministry of Education in collaboration with the Ministry of Communication and Digital Economy, should establish and enforce policies that guide internet usage in public secondary schools to safeguard students' academic and moral development.
- iv. **Guidance and Parental Monitoring:** School counsellors should actively provide guidance to students on responsible digital behaviour. In addition, parents must closely supervise their children's online activities at home to prevent misuse and excessive engagement with social media platforms.d

References

- Acquisti, A., & Gross, R. (2006). Imagined communities: Awareness, information sharing, and privacy on Facebook. Paper presented at the *6th workshop on Privacy Enhancing Technologies, Cambridge*.
- Adam, M. H., Zor, Z. A., & Oye, N. D. (2012). Students' perceptions on social networking sites influence on academic performance and virtual communities. *International Journal of Social Networking and Virtual communities*, 1(1), 7-15.
- Ajewola, O. O., & Fasola, O. S. (2012). A study of social network addiction among youth in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Science and Policy Review*, 4, 34-48.
- Asemah, E. Okpanachi, R., & Edegoh, L. (2013). Influence of social media on the academic performance of undergraduate students of Kogi State University, Anyigba, Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Science*, 3(12), 90-96.
- Boyd, D. M., & Ellison, N. B. (2007). Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), 210-230.
- Croteau, D., & Hoynes, W. (2003). *Media/society: Industries, images, and audiences* (3rd ed.). Pine Forge Press.
- Ellison, N. B., Stanfield, C., & Lampe, C. (2007). The benefits of Facebook "friends": Social capital and college students' use of online network sites. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 12(4), 1143-1168.
- Flaw, T. (2002). WTF: A crazy Brazilian invasion. In F. Sudweeks & H. Hrachovec (Eds.), *Proceedings of CATaC 2006* (pp.255-274). Murdoch University.
- Habib, M. K., Magruder-Habib, K. M., & Kupper, L. L. (1987). *Sample size determination in comparative studies* (Institute of Statistics Mimeo Series No. 1840). University of North Carolina.
- Jones, W. (2000). Social media and youth identity. *Journal of Media Studies*, 12(3), 1-12.
- Kalpidou, M., Costin, D., & Morris, J. (2011). The relationship between Facebook and the well-being of undergraduate college students. *Cyberpsychology, Behaviour, and Social Networking*, 14(4), 183-189.
- Manovich, L. (2001). *The Language of new media*. MIT Press.
- Mbaeze, I. C., Elochukwu, U., & Choima, A. (2010). The influence of information and communication technologies on students' academic performance. *Journal of Information Technology Impact*, 10(3), 129-136.
- McQuail, D. (1994). The rise of media of mass communication. In D. McQuail (Ed.), *Mass communication theory: An introduction* (pp. 1-29).
- McQuail, D. (2000). *McQuail's mass communication theory* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Ogundiji, O. (2014). Use of social networking among secondary school students: Implications for academic performance. *Scientific Research Journal (SCIRJ)*, 17-

34).

Schill, R. (2011). Social networking teens more likely to drink, use drugs, study finds.

Journalism and Media Issues. <https://jjie.org/teens-on-facebook-more-likely->

[drunk-or-use-drugs-study-finds](https://jjie.org/teens-on-facebook-more-likely-)

Tham, J., & Ahmed, N. (2011). The usage and implications of social networking sites:

A

survey of college students. *A Journal Interpersonal, Intercultural and Mass Communication*, 2(1), 1-11.